

DISCLOSURE OF KHOREZM DUTAR MAQAMS IN MUSIC LESSONS

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Annotation: This article covers the theoretical and practical aspects of studying Khorezm dutar maqams in music education. Khorezm dutar maqams, as an invaluable heritage of the musical culture of Uzbekistan, are of great importance in the formation of national music education for students. The article analyzes the history of Khorezm dutar maqams, their performance style, and the possibilities of developing aesthetic education and musical thinking in students through them. The article also considers innovative methods of covering these maqams in music lessons, the effectiveness of their use in the educational process, and advanced pedagogical approaches. The results of the research offer effective recommendations for teaching Khorezm dutar maqams.

Keywords: Khorezm dutar maqams, music education, national music culture, maqam performance, aesthetic education, musical thinking, innovative methods, music lesson.

Introduction.

The unique musical culture of Khorezm has been an integral part of the psyche of our people for thousands of years with its uniqueness and aesthetic beauty. Khorezm dutar maqams are a vivid example of this rich cultural heritage. Each of their melodies, each sound excites the human heart, revives the national spirit and expresses a unique spiritual world. Dutar maqams are valuable not only as a work of art, but also as a mirror of people's life, a musical expression of historical and cultural events. In today's era of globalization, in-depth teaching of national culture to the younger generation and leading them to spiritual perfection has become an extremely urgent issue. Music lessons play an important role in achieving this goal. In particular, by covering Khorezm dutar maqams in the lesson process, it is possible to enhance students' understanding of national values, develop musical thinking, and strengthen their sense of identity. This article is devoted to the uniqueness of Khorezm dutar maqams, the possibilities of their application in music education and their pedagogical significance.

Therefore, the article discusses the historical roots of dutar maqams, their musical characteristics and ways of effectively covering them in today's educational process. After all, passing on this rich heritage to the younger

generation is a tribute to our ancestors and a great responsibility to the future generation.

The importance of Khorezm dutar maqams in musical education:

Khorezm dutar maqams constitute a unique and unique part of the rich musical culture of Uzbekistan. They are not only a high example of national musical art, but also an invaluable heritage reflecting the historical, cultural and spiritual wealth of the people. The use of Khorezm dutar maqams in the process of musical education plays an important role in the understanding of national identity, the formation of aesthetic taste and the development of creative abilities in students.

Formation of national identity: Khorezm dutar maqoms allow students to understand their national roots. The content and melodies of each maqom are combined with national upbringing and values. In the process of studying these melodies, students feel the cultural heritage of their ancestors and form national pride.

Development of aesthetic taste and musical thinking: The elegance of the melodies and melodies of dutar maqoms forms aesthetic taste in children. The complex melodic structure of maqoms and the style of performance play a major role in developing musical thinking in students. This increases their musical literacy and increases interest in musical creativity.

Development of creative abilities: Studying dutar maqoms encourages students to take a creative approach. By understanding the subtleties of melodies and performing them, students develop their creative abilities. Also, performing maqoms increases technical skills and performance culture in students.

Preservation and promotion of cultural heritage: By highlighting Khorezm dutar maqoms in music education, this art can be preserved and passed on to future generations. Dutar maqoms, as an integral part of our national culture, deserve great attention in the international arena.

By teaching these melodies to the younger generation, Khorezm dutar maqams are of particular importance in music education with their educational, educational and creative aspects. Through them, students understand the richness and beauty of our national music and develop a desire for musical culture and spiritual perfection in themselves. Therefore, the widespread use of this rich heritage in the education system is necessary not only to preserve our culture, but also to ensure its continuation by the new generation.

Discussion.

Khorezm dutar maqams are of unparalleled importance in spiritually enriching students through the magical world of music and instilling respect for our national culture. These maqams are not just melodies, but are musical expressions of the historical feelings of the people, their philosophy of life and their delicate views on art. Therefore, the process of studying these works in music lessons not only improves performing skills, but also broadens the worldview of children, develops their aesthetic feelings.

The discussion considered several important aspects of teaching Khorezm dutar maqoms in the classroom. First of all, maqoms, as a key element of musical education, arouse students' interest in national culture. Because the deep content of maqoms and the emotional richness of their melodies capture the hearts of students and encourage them to self-realize through music. Secondly, in the process of studying these maqoms, a creative approach is formed in students. Performing dutar melodies requires not only technical skill, but also a sense of the inner meaning of the musical work. This serves to develop musical thinking and creative thinking in children. Modern methods of using Khorezm dutar maqoms in lessons are also important. Interactive coverage of the history of maqoms, structural features of melodies, and their place in our national culture using innovative technologies increases efficiency. For example, presenting maqom performances in video and audio formats through digital platforms will increase students' interest and create opportunities for deeper analysis. By widely introducing Khorezm dutar maqoms in music education, it is possible to convey our national heritage to the younger generation and enrich them spiritually and aesthetically. This process not only develops students' creativity, but also serves such lofty goals as understanding national identity and appreciating historical values. Therefore, every teacher should contribute to conveying this rich heritage to the new generation.

Conclusion.

Khorezm dutar maqoms are a masterpiece of our national music, and they are not only a collection of melodies and melodies, but also a symbol of the soulful experiences, philosophy of life and culture of our people. Conveying this rich heritage to students through music education is not only a scientific, but also a spiritual responsibility. Today, covering Khorezm dutar maqoms in music lessons is one of the most effective ways to lead the younger generation to aesthetic and spiritual perfection.

Studying dutar maqoms in the lesson process, on the one hand, increases students' musical literacy, and on the other hand, forms interest in and respect

for national values. Since each melody and tone expresses its own story and content, students understand their historical and cultural roots through music. This is an important factor in their spiritual development.

At the same time, the use of innovative approaches and modern methods in lessons makes the process of teaching Khorezm dutor maqoms more interesting and effective. Teaching students the history and performance styles of maqoms using interactive tools, audio-visual materials, and digital technologies not only enriches the process, but also increases students' interest in music.

Studying Khorezm dutor maqoms is not only a part of music education, but also serves the great goal of self-awareness, awakening national pride, and conveying a rich cultural heritage to the future generation. On this path, every teacher, every educator should strive to convey these values to the younger generation with their creative approach and knowledge. After all, our national music is a living reflection of our national spirit. And preserving and developing this heritage is the duty of all of us.

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